

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13963052

Dimensions Of Use Of Social Media Administration Of Public Secondary School In Afikpo Zone

¹Aja-Okorie, Uzoma & ²Okoro Mkpuma

¹Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria

²Ebonyi State college of Education, Ikwo, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study, investigated Dimensions of social media in Administration of public Secondary School Principals in Ebonyi State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study used descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 452 principals of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. There was no sampling because the population served as the sample. The researcher developed a 40- items structured questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 0.73 titled 'Dimensions of use of social media on Administration of Public Secondary School in Afikpo Zone. (DOSMAOPSSAZ). The instrument was validated by (3) lecturers; two from Department of Educational Foundations (Educational Administration and Planning option) and one from Measurement and Evaluation option of the Department of Science Education, all in Ebonyi state university Abakaliki. The reliability measures of internal consistency, using the Cronbach Alpha method yielded an overall reliability index of 0.73. data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and t-test of independence statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that public secondary school principals in Ebonyi state can leverage on social media to enhance communication with staff, manage conflicts among staff, enhance school-community collaboration, encourage teamwork among staff and ensure equitable sharing of instructional resources. In addition, there was no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural principals on their use of social-media to enhance communication with staff, manage conflicts among staff, enhance school- community collaboration, encourage teamwork among staff and ensure equitable sharing of instructional resources. Based on findings of the study, it was recommended among others that; principals should embrace social media platform to facilitate quick communication with staff and ensure the attainment of balance in way to strengthen communication with stakeholders.

Keywords; Dimensions of use of social media in administration of public secondary school.

INTRODUCTION

The value of Social Media in modern day living cannot be underestimated. The phenomenon of Social Media has undergone significant growth and has emerged as a pivotal component in individuals' everyday routines (Alabi, 2017). The impact of this phenomenon is particularly evident in the realm of education, as educational institutions and students are progressively utilizing Social Media platforms for communication and interaction purposes (Kiruriti, 2015). According to Ugwuzor, (2017), the utilization of social media in educational communication management has significant opportunities within the dynamic landscape of the digital era. This medium therefore, holds the potential to enhance information accessibility, foster knowledge sharing, and facilitate cooperation among administrators, staff and students. Ogunbiyi, (2017) noted that Social Media platforms have the potential to serve as a valuable instrument for fostering community engagement and enhancing involvement in educational endeavors.

Social Media refers to digital platforms that facilitate user interaction, content sharing, and online communication. According to Joo, (2020), these platforms provide users the ability to generate individual profiles or pages, transmit messages, distribute images, videos, and other types of information, and engage in many social endeavors. Several well-known social media platforms include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, YouTube, WhatsApp, among others. There is no clear and distinct definition of what the term Social Media really is. However, this study will toll the line of research evidence where researchers have consistently focused on specified applications or platforms, though, in divergent contexts. For instance, “twitter” (Olowo, Fashiku, Adebakin, & Ajadi, 2020), “Facebook” (Lim, 2012). What is obvious in all the definitions above is that, all the authors appear to have agreed that social media involves the usage of online technologies for interactions. In this paper therefore, the term “social media” therefore can be understood to mean all internet-based applications or platforms which are developed to facilitate interactions, communication including networking which may include applications such as “blogs and micro blogs (twitter), wikis (Wikipedia), social networking (Facebook, LinkedIn), multimedia sharing services (YouTube, Netflix), content syndication (like RSS feeds), podcasting and content tagging services.

The remarkable technological breakthrough of the 21st century has brought about marked increase in the availability and use of social media applications and platforms. The social media has become a resource for transformative information because it appears to have remolded and significantly revolutionized how individuals now communicate and socialize. No doubt, social media plays a critical role in information dissemination, be it casual, sensational, sensitive, or even political information. Social media platforms vary in terms of their features and functionality; nonetheless, their primary objective is to enable users to engage in social interactions and exchange information. The advent of social media platforms has significantly transformed the manner in which individuals engage in communication, interact with one another, and disseminate information (Oredein, O. 2016). As noted by Chen and Wang (2021), Social media platforms have emerged as a significant medium for disseminating news, advocating for ideas, endorsing products or services, and establishing both social and professional connections. It is imperative here to note that sharing idea. In the context of this study Social Media is an administrative tools or strategies adopted by the principals of secondary schools for sharing of information, idea, knowledge and skills to the students or staff.

Secondary school administration has to do with the management of school affairs as an organization. According to Ogunbiyi (2017), school administration in general is the process of using human and material resources available in schools to get things done in order to achieve goals already established by the school. The author further enunciated that school administration is a goal-oriented intention; hence it is about the management of the resources economically and effectively. This is in order to maximize the advantages and minimize disadvantages for the system being administered. School administration involves principals working with staff, students, and community for the achievement of goals. It involves the use of men, materials and funds to achieve set objectives (Ugwuanyi, 2013). According to Alabi (2017), the most vital aspect of school as an organization is the attainment of organizational goals and objectives. Therefore, without proper and careful administration, use of good resources and involvement of groups, the goals of secondary school education as stated by the National Policy on Education will not be achieved. Alabi (2017) defined administration has to do with; policy, leadership and management activities engaged in by people who occupy position of formal responsibility and authority in an organization; coordinating the efforts of people towards the achievement of their set out goals; and the polices of the Board of Education. From the foregoing, one can assert that administration is a purposeful effort which has to do with bringing both human and material resources together in an organized manner to achieve some stated goals and objectives of an organization. The main objective of administration in any organization is that of planning, coordinating, directing, controlling the efforts of peoples towards the achievement of goals (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2014). In the context of this study, secondary school administration is the process of bringing staff, students and community together through Social media platform in order to achieve the stated goals and objectives of education. Thus, administration in secondary schools in modern time cannot happen without embracing modern technological media.

In School administration, Social Media packages can be selected by school administrators to exchange information, express ideas, and share sentiments through listening, accuracy, and clarity of

information are referred to as communication strategies (Tarigan, Harahap, Sari, Sakinah, & Ausat, 2023). Communication abilities are a crucial component of conflict management in improving job performance, according to research on conflict management strategies (Olowo, 2020). Principals could use Social Media platforms to effectively communicate with parents and teachers, make announcements, or advise them of upcoming events at the school. Tarigan et al., (2023) made a similar argument, claiming that principals may use these social networks to interact with one another, collaborate, inform stakeholders, cultivate relationship, gather resources, solicit input, receive support, and share ideas, data, strategies, and information. It is becoming clear that effective communication is crucial for building trust between administrators and teachers and that positive interaction are crucial for assisting teachers in becoming successful educators. Therefore, according to Ugwuanyi, F. N. (2013), principals can utilize Social Media to ensure accurate and timely communication with staff members in the school. According to Oredein (2013), in particular, Social Media aids administrators in reaching decisions with teachers on the best ways to advance school development, particularly in relation to students' academic achievement.

In addition, the use of Social Media applications or packages can be also instrumental in speedy and timely management of conflicts among staff (Tyler, 2016). Conflicts, according to Kiruriti (2015), are disagreements between two or more persons or groups when each party is vying for the acceptance of their viewpoint over the others. According to Lussier (2015), conflicts are instances in which individuals are at odds with one another over ideologies, values, or other aspects of culture, politics, or religion. Thus, conflicts can be understood as disagreements or disputes between two or more opposing parties who have divergent interests, ideas, attitudes, values, and objectives. Conflicts in schools have reportedly disrupted learning environments, causing confusion and discord. Conflicts create an uncomfortable, disruptive, and stressful work environment that lowers employee productivity (Tyler, 2016). Omene (2021) submitted that in order to achieve successful organizational performance and the findings indicated that doing so would increase productivity and produce improved decision-making. In this study, effort would be intensified to find out how leveraging on Social Media as a medium would serve as an efficient conflict management technique which will boost effective teamwork among staff and students. However, the extent principals use Social Media applications or packages may vary depending on school location.

Location denotes the physical attributes of a school which distinguished it from another school in terms of buildings, materials, access road, pipe bone water, electricity, human beings among others. Okorie and Ezech (2016) defined a school location as a particular place, in relation to other areas in the physical environment (rural or urban), where the school is sited. Human beings have unlimited capacity to learn, but many however be limited by the behavior patterns and facilities that the immediate school environment offers (Oredein, 2016). According to Idialu (2013) urban areas are those thickly populated towns or cities with the basic amenities (electricity, good road, good health facilities and internet facilities, etc.) that make life comfortable, while rural areas are those places distinguished from towns and cities with little or no basic amenities or facilities. It is important to note that with the advancement of urbanization, the educational opportunities of urban-rural social members are also changing fundamentally: both in scale and quantity, and the educational opportunities have been significantly improved. The urban and rural difference not only embodies in the economic field, but also leads to the unequal allocation of educational resources between urban and rural areas. For instance, there are usually poor network coverage, low installation of electric gadgets, and poor supply of electricity in rural schools which could make it impossible for principals to use Social Media applications effectively and efficiently; but in urban areas, there are good network coverage, relatively electricity supply and installed network gadgets that support Social media usage in schools. This situation was supported by the idea of Yu-you and Zhi-hui (2017) that under the education system of urban-rural separation, the "urban priority" policy causes serious differences in educational level. On the one hand, Alabi (2017) note that the narrowing of the gap between urban and rural investment in education can hardly conceal the actual gap in the level and quality of basic education between urban and rural areas.

The differences in rural and urban secondary schools in Ebonyi State may manifest in the different use of Social Media packages in the administration of secondary schools. For instance, Yu-you, & Zhi-hui (2017) & Rahmadi (2020) averred that the use of Social Media is more prevalent in

communities with internet facilities and regular electricity supply. However, Joo (2020) established that locality is not primarily the determinant of choice to use the social media in school administration. The inconsistencies in research regarding the influence of location, on the use of Social Media in school administration necessitate further investigation in this regard. However, considering the immense benefits that Social Media as a social media has been espoused to bring to the development of education but with little or no evidence-based research on the impacts it exerts on principals' administrative effectiveness, it becomes imperative to investigate the Social Media usage in the administration of secondary school principals of Ebonyi State.

Statement Of Problems

The emergence of social networking sites referred to as social media in this study, which is enabled through Android phones and its likes, birthed a novel way of information exchange and human activities generally. This development also permeates in the life and administrative responsibilities of secondary school principals. The coming of Android phone which started as a hobby for some literate people has become the easy means of communication with the stakeholders in education sector including teachers, students, parents, and the community at large. Implying that there is need to embrace the gain social media platforms can offer to ensure effective and timely reach-out to key stakeholders. In particular, social media application can offered effective communication with staff personnel in resolving problems that could have given rise to detrimental impacts on all parties involved and the school. Social media application can aid principals in Ebonyi state in resolving issues affecting staff personnel, can effectively communicate to host communities, and reaching other stakeholders in discussing issues that can affect the school. In other words, principals can use social media application to pass information as quick as possible unlike letter writing or other forms of communication in the past. Evidence from researches in the background of the study have suggested that using online technologies can encourage online discussion among teachers and students outside the classroom, beyond the traditional class setting, which can be instrumental in solving individual students' problems. However, irrespective of the benefits social media platforms can offer in education and in school administration in particular, most principals seem not to use it in school administration. The researcher's sordid visit and interaction with some school principals' indicates that most of them lack skills and ability of handling social media sites or knowledge of video conferencing in organizing meetings in school's administration. This could have contributed to difficulties of public secondary schools engaging in school activities in distress periods like the global Corona Virus pandemic (Covid-19). For instant, it was difficult for principals to reach out to their students or staff because of the inability to handle social media platforms.

Although, notable differences in the location of schools in terms of network coverage, installation of electrical appliances, knowledge of technological usage, lack of electrical power supply can hinder the use of Social Media in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Nevertheless, there is still little to embrace social media usage. In addition, there is paucity of studies on the extent of use of Social Media by principals in the administration of public secondary schools. Therefore, the problem of this study is to determine principals' use of Social Media in administration of secondary school in Ebonyi State with school location as the moderating variable.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the influence of social media usage on administration of secondary school principals of Ebonyi state. Specifically, the study determined

1. Extent principals' use social media to encourage communication among staff in secondary school administration in Ebonyi state.
2. Extent principals' use social media to manage conflicts among staff in secondary school administration in Ebonyi state

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent do principals use social media to encourage communication among staff in secondary school administration in Ebonyi state?
2. To what extent do principals' use social media to manage conflicts among staff secondary school administration in Ebonyi state?

Hypotheses

The following two (2) null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO1: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of rural and urban school principals on the extent principals’ use social media to encourage communication among staff secondary schools in Ebonyi state.

HO2: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of rural and urban school principals on the extent principals’ use social media to manage conflicts among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi6 state.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. In descriptive study, the researcher can use instrument like questionnaire, checklist, interview and observational schedules among others to collect data from a large population. The choice of this design was because it enables the researcher to have in-depth knowledge on the social media in the administration of secondary school principals’ of Ebonyi state using questionnaire and descriptive statistics without manipulation of independent variable. The population of the study comprised four hundred and fifty- two (452) junior and senior principals from 226 public secondary schools in Ebonyi state (source: SEB,2023). Sampling technique used was census because all the 452 principals’ were used for the study since the population is manageable. The instrument for data collection was 40 items structured questionnaire on principals use of social media in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi state.

RESULTS

The data collected were presented in tables based on the two research questions developed from the objectives of the study.

Research Question 1: *To what extent do principals’ use Social Media to encourage communication among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State?*

In Table 1 below, data gotten from respondents were analysed to show the extent principals use social media to encourage communication among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Table 1: Mean responses of the respondents on the extent principals’ use Social Media to encourage communications among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State

S/N	Items	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
1	Social media applications are used to share needed learning materials quickly to teachers and students	396	3.44	0.49	Often
2	Social media packages are used to send short messages to staff and students	396	3.18	0.38	Often
3	Serves as a tool to understand staff feelings that affect teaching and learning in School	396	3.30	0.59	Often
4	Used by principals to discuss teaching materials with teachers	396	2.18	0.54	Rarely
5	Video conferencing is used to have emergency meeting with staff	396	3.17	0.75	Often
6	Social media packages are used to enhance the capabilities of teamwork	396	2.19	0.39	Rarely
7	Social media applications are used for discussion that aids problem solving in school	396	2.24	0.43	Rarely
8	Social media packages are used to encourage teachers that are introvert to air their view on school programmes.	396	1.39	0.49	Never
9	Social media is used by principals to get quick feedback from stakeholders	396	3.68	0.47	Always

Result in table 1 showed that principals always use social media to exercise item9, often use it for items 1, 2, 3, and 5 and rarely use it for items 4, 6 and 7 to encourage communication among staff in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do principals' use Social Media to manage conflicts among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State?*

In table2 below, data gotten from respondents were analysed to show the extent principals use social media to manage conflicts among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Table 2: Mean responses of the respondents on the extent principals' use Social Media to manage conflicts among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State

S/N	Items: Use of Social Media help principals to:	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
10	engage in long-close conversation with parties involved in conflict to understand their complaints without necessarily meeting them in persons	396	2.18	0.38	Rarely
11	initiate promptness in communicating with conflicting staffs which helps him/her resolve it in quick time	396	2.24	0.43	Rarely
12	create clarity in communication while resolving conflicts between staffs	396	3.18	0.39	Often
13	build confidentiality in communication with conflicting staff which enhances conflict management	396	3.24	0.43	Often
14	maintain assertiveness in communication which enhances conflict resolution in the school	396	3.11	0.49	Often
15	build quality listening skill which enhances his/her conflict management among staff	396	1.26	0.44	Never
16	build flexibility and openness in dealing with conflicts at school	396	3.18	0.76	Often
17	empathize with conflicting party's individual which helps in dealing with conflicts effectively	396	2.11	0.49	Rarely
18	secretly inquire from other staffs regarding issues with the conflicting staff	396	2.32	0.47	Rarely

Result in table2 showed that principals often use social media on items 12, 13, 14 and 16, rarely use them on items 10, 11, 17 and 18, and never use them to manage conflicts among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State as indicated on item 15.

DISCUSSIONS

Findings of the study revealed that principals in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State often use social media to share needed learning material quickly to teachers and students, send short messages to staff and students and to understand staff feelings that affect teaching and learning in school. In addition, it was revealed that principals rarely use social media to; discuss teaching materials with teachers, enhance the capabilities of teamwork, engage in discussions that aid problem-solving in school, and often use video conferencing to have emergency meetings with staff. However, it was revealed that principals never used social packages to encourage teachers that are introvert to air their views on school programmes but are always used to get quick feedback from stakeholders. Furthermore, the mean responses of urban and rural principals on their use of social media to enhance communication among staff in secondary school administration in Ebonyi State was not statistically different. The finding is in tandem with that of Olowo, Fashiku, Adebakin & Ajadi, (2020) who examined the effectiveness of Ekiti State secondary school principals in disseminating information using social media and found that the principals always use social media to disseminate information among staff, students and other stakeholders. Equally, the finding aligns with that of Ugwuanyi (2013) who determined the extent of principals' utilization of social networking sites for enhancing communication in secondary schools in Anambra State and found that there was high extent of principals' utilization of WhatsApp for enhancing communication in secondary schools in Anambra State. Furthermore, the finding is in tandem to that Cox and McLeod (2014) who qualitatively described, analyzed, and interpreted the experiences of school principals who use multiple social media tools with stakeholders as part of their comprehensive communications practices and found that social media tools allow for greater interactions between school principals and their stakeholders, provide stronger connections to local stakeholders, to fellow educators, and to the world. Furthermore, the responses of the respondents which revealed no significant difference showed that social media

can be a fundamental tool which principals of secondary schools can depend on to ensure effectiveness in school administration with respect to communicating effectively among staff. This is substantiated in research by Olowo et al. (2020) Tarigan et al. (2023) who reported in their different studies that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from different regions regarding the impact of social media in ensuring effective communication between principals and the staff. This implies that social media tools can be utilized by secondary school principals to effectively communicate with staff, students and other stakeholders in their day-to-day administration of the school.

On conflict management, the study finding revealed that principals rarely use social media to engage in long-close conversation with parties involved in conflict to; understand their complaints without necessarily meeting them in person, and empathize with conflicting party's individual which helps in dealing with conflicts effectively. In addition, the principals rarely use social media to; initiate promptness in communicating with conflicting staffs which helps him/her resolve it in quick time, secretly inquire from other staffs regarding issues with the conflicting staff and never used them to build quality listening skill which enhances his/her conflict management among staff. However, the findings also revealed that principals often leverage on social media tool to; create clarity in communication while resolving conflicts between staffs, build confidentiality in communication with conflicting staff which enhances conflict management, maintains assertiveness in communication which enhances conflict resolution in the school, and build flexibility and openness in dealing with conflicts at school. More so, there was no significant difference in the mean responses of urban and rural principals on their use of social media to enhance conflict management in the course of administering the school. The findings align with that of Joo, (2020) who investigated the influence of the WhatsApp application on decision making processes among kindergarten-managers in Israel and found that principals leverage on social media tool like WhatsApp to effectively broaden their decision-making scope in all kind of issues (conflict management inclusive). This is corroborated by JOO (2020), Chen & Wang, (2021) who determined the extent of principals' utilization of social networking sites for enhancing communication in secondary schools in Anambra State and found that principals use WhatsApp extensively to engage with the staff. Furthermore, the responses of the respondents which showed no significant difference goes to show that social media can be an instrumental tool which principals of secondary schools can rely on to ensure effective school administration especially as it concerns conflict management among staff. This is corroborated by Tamir et al. (2020) and Kiruriti (2015) who reported in their different studies that no significant difference was recorded among respondents from different regions.

Educational implication of the study.

The study findings have demonstrated social media can be utilized by principals to ensure effective administration of the school. This is important because social media platform can be used to enhance communication, manage conflicts because it guarantees, maintain effective school- community collaboration, encourage teamwork among staff and ensure equitable distribution of instructional resources. Thus it is imperative that secondary school principals in Ebonyi state embrace the use of social media platform as a means to sustainable end in ensuring effective administration of the school due to their proven efficacy.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that to ensure effective administration of the schools, public secondary school principals in Ebonyi State can be leveraged on social media platforms to enhance communication with staff and manage conflicts among staff.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings of the study recommends that secondary school principals should embrace social media platforms to enhance communication with staff. In addition, the principals can use the flexibility and ease of social media to facilitate mediate easily to resolve conflicts among staff.

Authors Contribution

Mkpuma, Okoro: Developed the content of the study

Prof. U. Aja-Okrie: Reviewed the content of the study

REFERENCES

- Alabi, A. O. (2017). Records Keeping For Effective Administration of Secondary Schools. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 7(2), 66. Retrieved on 11th July 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.5296/jpag.v7i2.11182>.
- Chen, J., & Wang, Y. (2021). Social Media Use for Health Purposes: Systematic Review. *Journal of Mediterranean Internet Research*, 23(5), 17-27.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Joo, Y.H. (2020). The Effects of Distributed Leadership on Teacher Professionalism: The Case of Korean Middle Schools. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99(3), 101-105.
- Kiruriti, J. M. (2015) The obstacles faced by female educational administrators in educational administration in Mombasa country, kenya. Masters dissertation, university of kenya.
- Ogunbiyi O. D. (2017). Influence of community participation on the administration of public secondary schools in Benue State. A Thesis Submitted to the Department of Educational Foundations and General Studies, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi
- Olowo, B.F., Fashiku, C.O., Adebakin, A.B., & Ajadi, O.T. (2020). Social media: a modern tool to enhance communication skills of the secondary school principals in Ekiti State. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 16(2), 97 – 108.
- Oredein, O. (2016). *Effects of school variables on students' academic performance in municipal area of Cross River State*. Calabar: University Publication
- Rahmadi, F. (2020). WhatsApp Group for Teaching and Learning in Indonesian higher education: What's Up? *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 14(13), 150-160. Retrieved on 12th march 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v14i13.14121>.
- Tarigan, I.M., Harahap, M. A. K., Sari, D. M., Sakinah, R. D., & Ausat, A. M. A. (2023). Understanding Social Media: Benefits of Social Media for individuals. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 7(1), 2317–2322. Retrieved on 12th June, 2023 from <https://jptam.org/index.php/jptam/article/view/5559>
- Ugwuanyi, F. N. (2013). *Community Participation in the Administration of Secondary Schools in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State*. B. Ed project, Department of Educational Foundations, U.N.N. 126p.
- Yu-you, Q., & Zhi-hui, W.U. (2017). Research on the conditions and the future development thoughts of rural education in China. *Journal of Northeast Normal University (Philosophy and Social Sciences)*, 2(3), 1-8.